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Socioeconomic Status And Access To Maternal Health Care Services In Lafia L.G.A, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Socioeconomic status of an individual such as level of income, education, employment etc determine people access to quality healthcare services in most part of the world. The main objective of the paper is to examine the influence of socioeconomic status on access to healthcare services in Lafia Local Government Area. Multistage sampling technique was used for the study with Yamane formular used to determine the sample size of 400 while rational choice theory serve as a theoretical framework of the study. Findings shows that income, education, occupation are correlated with access to maternal healthcare services in Lafia LGA therefore, the study recommends expansion of health insurance scheme/agency to local farmers, unemployed women and other business men towards increasing access to maternal healthcare services

Keywords: Socioeconomic, access, maternal healthcare

INTRODUCTION

Maternal health has remained a global concern because a lot of women do not have access to maternal health care services and are still losing their lives to pregnancy and child birth related complications. Motherhood could be a joyful and fulfilling experience but for too many women it could be associated with complications, injuries, disabilities and sometimes death (WHO, 2016). Although there has been a 47% decline in maternal deaths globally, the maternal mortality ratio is still unacceptably high (Maigwa, 2017). With an estimated poor utilization of maternal health facilities and maternal mortality ratio of 500 per 100,000 live births; sub-Saharan Africa accounts for 56% of all maternal deaths globally and poor access to maternal health services (United Nations Population Fund, 2015). Delivery in a health facility is associated with lower maternal and newborn mortality and morbidity rates compared with home delivery (Stephenson, Baschieri, Clements, Hennink & Madise, 2016).

Socio-economic status such as levels of education or health literacy and poverty can impact maternal health-seeking behaviour including access and utilization of health care services (Ariyo et al., 2017; Azuh et al., 2015; Marchie, 2012; Marchie & Anyanwu, 2009; Odekunle, 2016; Ogu et al., 2016). According to a study conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics, the adult literacy rate in Nigeria is 56.9% with variation between states (e.g., Lagos at 92%; Borno at 14.5%), regions (e.g., South West – 69.1%; NorthWest – 31.7%), and gender (e.g., males – 65.1%; females - 48.6%) (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO, 2012). In addition, about 105 million Nigerians currently live in extreme poverty from 98 million in October 2019 (World Poverty Clock, 2020) making Nigeria a

poverty-stricken country. Moreover, in Nigeria several studies (Chukwudebelu & Ozumba, 2017; Oguniyi & Faleyemu, 2015) have shown that poor maternal health is more common among women in lower socioeconomic class when indices such as education, income level and types of housing are used. However, there is no clear-cut studies in respect of these factors in Lafia Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, therefore, this study is an attempt to bridge the gap in the study

Literature review and theoretical framework

2.1 Socio-economic Status

Socioeconomic status of households and families also has a key role to play in relation to accessing maternal healthcare in the society. Socioeconomic status refers to the income level and standard of living of a family/household. In rural Nigeria, most households live below poverty line and have low standard of living and this is a situation which places them in a subordinate condition in the society. As a result of this, their access to maternal healthcare services will be influenced based on their income level.

According to the Demographic Health Survey (2018), only 35% of Nigerian women deliver in hospitals and increasingly high cost of health service has further plunged people into the poverty divide thus leading to problem in seeking treatment from health centers. Many of the common causes of maternal complications and mortality in Nigeria are readily preventable, detectable and manageable. Key interventions such as insurance, assisted living have been identified and used to improve maternal health care in many countries. However, the use of such interventions has been found to be limited in developing countries like Nigeria (Jowett, 2014). One of the reasons for this is the level of health care financing and poor insurance coverage.

However, Abutu (2018) is of the view that going by such programmes as the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), Maternal and Under-5 Child Health care project (MCH) already lunched in six states, the possibilities of Nigeria meeting the health component of the Millennium Development Goal (MDGs) is bright. Today, the NHIA cut across all states of the federation and several state governments initiated their health scheme thus, Nasarawa State Health Insurance Agency is put in place. According to him, the project will help to eliminate physical and financial barriers to qualitative care for pregnant women and children less than five years. But the question is, how effective are these programmes in the rural areas of the country? Many analysts are of the views that like most other programmes in Nigeria, corruption will not allow these programmes to make any serious impact (Abutu, 2018).

Health policies and programmes in Nasarawa state are directed towards the creation of a basic infrastructure and adequate manpower for the effective delivery of health services for the rapidly growing population. In 2010, there were 650 government and private health facilities care providing maternal care service distributed throughout the state. These include 623 primary and 27 secondary health care facilities. The number increased steadily to 1,290 in 2019, representing an additional 640- almost twice what it was a decade earlier (Nasarawa State Ministry of Health, 2017). On hierarchical distribution of health care facilities in the state from 2010-2019, there were 623 primary health care facilities in the year 2000 and the figure rose to 1,245 an additional 622 in 2009. The number of secondary health care facilities similarly rose from 27 in the year 2000 to 43 in 2009 representing an additional 16 secondary health facilities. Two tertiary health care centers were established in 2001 namely; Federal Medical Centre Keffi and Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital Lafia, which account for only 0.2 percent to complement health care service delivery in the state.

The tertiary health services are exclusively in the urban areas serving as referral centers. In 2009, general and private hospitals which provide secondary health services in the state account for about 3.3 percent while 96.5 percent of health care establishments in the state are concerned with primary health care delivery (Nasarawa State Ministry of Health, 2017). Primary health care mainly provides first aid health care services, preventive health care and limited medical care such as maternity services. Generally, they are the first point of call whenever people fall ill especially in the rural communities where there are no

hospitals. The facilities in the primary health centers are largely managed by nurses, midwives and community health workers. The distribution and accessibility of these health services is therefore important in the rural communities. Today, in Nasarawa, there exist a Federal University of Lafia Teaching Hospital and a host of other newly established general hospitals and primary healthcare centre, the challenges are effective services delivery and the cost of services.

2.2 Maternal Health

Maternal and child health is crucial, not just because it is an index for measuring the efficiency of the health care system but more importantly because of what it portends for the future and generations to come. In countries where maternal child health indices are poor, the future potential of entire communities is bleak (Loto & Okogbo, 2018). This is because the health of mothers and children are essential for the economic growth and development of nations. Maternal health care is the health service provided to women in their child bearing age. The targets for maternal health are all women in their reproductive age groups, i.e., 15-49 years of age. Throughout the world, especially in the developing countries, there is an increasing concern and interest in maternal health care. This commitment towards maternal health care gains further strength after the World Summit for Children, 1991, which gave serious consideration and outlined major areas to be addressed in the provision of Maternal and Child Health Care services.

Maternal health refers to the health of women before and during pregnancy, at childbirth and during the postpartum period (WHO, 2017). Before pregnancy, the overall health and lifestyle choices of parents can affect fertility, maternal health and their infants' probability of developing chronic conditions later in life. Screening for people contemplating pregnancy for health problems, which need to be identified and managed characterizes maternal health. During pregnancy, maternal health is the high-quality maternal care that is essential to ensure not only a healthy pregnancy for mother and baby but also an effective transition to positive labour and childbirth.

Services include the provision of education and basic easily understood information on health care for expectant parents. During delivery, high-quality, evidence-based obstetric and neonatal care is one of the highest priorities to reduce illness and death in mothers and their newborn babies. In the postpartum period, it is critical to monitor maternal and newborn health as the risk of death is higher during the first week of postpartum for both. Timely detection and management of symptoms reduce the risk of mortality and complications (WHO, 2017).

Services over these stages of maternal health care include, but not limited to, access to sexual and reproductive health services; nutritional advice; screening and management of communicable diseases and non-communicable diseases (NCDs); gender-based violence prevention and response; and risk detection and management (WHO, 2015). While it remains important to prioritize the unfinished agenda with regards to maternal health, it is also important to recognize maternal health services as one essential part of the continuum of care for women. Placing women's health within a life-course perspective can yield benefits in the health of all women, whether or not they opt to become mothers (Harris, Resquejo & Bustreo, 2016).

2.3 Rational Choice Theory

The rational choice theory, also known as choice theory or rational action theory, is a theory for understanding and often modelling social and individual behaviour. Rational choice theory was early popularized by a 1992 Nobel Memorial Prize Laureate in Economics Science, Gary Becker, who was one of the first to apply rational actor models more widely. According to Becker (1976), when faced with several courses of action, people usually do what they believe is likely to have the best overall outcome. The 'rationality' defined by the rational choice theory adopts a more specific and narrower definition, which simply means that an individual acts as if balancing costs against benefits to arrive at action that maximizes personal advantage (Friedman, 1953).

People always take decisions based on the perceived benefits with little cost. So, women and families will most likely access maternal health services if they believe that they have much to gain with little cost. When the cost is high, it serves as a barrier and will limit women from accessing maternal health care service. Poverty, distance among others can be limiting factors for certain people, thereby affecting their desire to access healthcare service during pregnancy.

The theory is criticized due to problems associated with inadequate information and uncertainty. This may make it difficult for individuals to make rational decisions. As a result, they may rely on other ways of making decisions. Also, human social action and interactions are complex, therefore limiting how accurate the theory is in explaining behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Lafia L.G.A. Lafia is populated mainly by the Eggon, Alago, Kanuri, Aho, Koro, Igbo, Hausa, Mwaghavul among other tribes. Lafia is an agrarian society with the farmers taking full advantage of the fertile, well-drained arable land suitable for the cultivation of cassava, yams, millet, sorghum, rice, citrus fruits, palm produce, vegetables and livestock thus contributing to socio economic development of Nasarawa State.

Generally, the people are sociable, receptive and hospitable. According to Independent National Electoral Commission (2021), Lafia has total registered voters of 247,231 populations. Therefore, the study area will focus on the total number of registered voters who are eighteen years and above. For the purpose of this study, the research calculated the sample size using Yamane (1967) sample size determination formula. The formula contains 0.010, 0.09, 0.07 and 0.05 margin error. For the purpose of this study, 0.05 margin error was used. Thus, see the solution below: The formula is thus $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

The formula is thus $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$:

Where;

n= Sample size

N= Total number of population of the study area (247,231)

1= Constant

e^2 = the coefficient of degree of error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Substituting into the formula;

$$n = \frac{247,231}{1 + 247,231 (0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{247,231}{247,232 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{247,231}{618.08}$$

$$n = 399.99$$

n = 400.

To determine the number of respondents from each ward using Bowley's representative method, the formular is a $n_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$ Where;

n = sample size,

nN_h = population of a strata and

N=total population

Table 1: Selected Political Wards

S/N	ELECTORAL WARDS	POPULATIONS OF THE ELECTORAL WARDS	SIZE	TOTAL QUESTIONNAIRES TO BE ADMINISTERED IN EACH WARD
1	CIROMA	50,611	$50,611 \times 400 = \frac{20244400}{133,910}$	151
2	GAYAM	28,898	$28,898 \times 400 = \frac{11559200}{133,910}$	86
3	BAKIN RIJIYA/ AKRUBA/ SARKIN PADA	21,208	$21,208 \times 400 = \frac{8483200}{133,910}$	64
4	MAKAMA	11,071	$11,071 \times 400 = \frac{4428400}{133,910}$	33
5	SHABU	22,122	$22,122 \times 400 = \frac{8848800}{133,910}$	66
	TOTAL	133,910		400

Source: INEC, 2021/Author's computation, 2024

Multistage sampling technique was used, involving the simple random and systematic sampling technique. The simple random selection technique was used in selecting the wards and polling units under Lafia Local Government Area. By using simple random sampling, the researcher applied fishbowl or lottery method in the sample selection whereby papers containing all the names of the wards were put in a basket. Lafia Local Government Area has 13 wards, namely Adogi, Agyaragun Tofa, Arikya, Ashigie, Assakio, Bakin Rijiya/akurba/sarkinPada, Chiroma, Gayam, Keffin/wambai, Makama, Shabu/kwandere and Wakwa and Zanwa. From these wards, five (5) were randomly selected for the purpose of this study which include Ciroma, Gayyam, Bakin Rijiya/Akurba/Sarkin Pada, Shabu/Kwandere and Makama Ward. This was done to eliminate bias and give equal chance of participation to all the wards and polling units in Lafia L.G.A. It was done to give equal opportunity to all the wards to take part in the study.

The systematic sampling technique was used at selecting the respondents from each ward. Thus 400 respondents were selected and these included; women who are within the reproduction age and women who have given birth. The reason for this adoption is due to the fact that the study area is large and cannot be totally studied by the researcher given the time frame. Since there is primary health care numbering that was used as a frame whereby every third house was selected and asked whether there is a woman of reproductive age or who once gave birth which was selected.

RESULTS

Four hundred questionnaires were distributed; three hundred and ninety (391) questionnaires were successfully retrieved while nine (9) questionnaires were not returned. Therefore, the findings from three hundred and ninety-one (391) respondents which represent 98% of the sample were collected and analyzed and constituted the 100%.

Table 2: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age		
15-19	27	7
20-24	56	14.3
25-29	101	25.8
30-34	89	22.8
35-39	78	19.9
40-44	32	8.2
45-49	8	2
Total	391	100
Sex		
Male	123	31.5
Female	268	68.5
Total	391	100
Marital status		
Single	80	20.5
Married	176	45
Divorced	36	9.2
Widowed	99	25.3
Total	391	100
Occupation		
Farming	102	26
Civil servant	96	24.6
Business	154	39.4
Student	39	10
Others	--	--
Total	391	100
Education		
Primary	192	49.1
Secondary	109	27.9
Tertiary	55	14.1
No formal Education	35	8.9
Total	391	100
Level of income		
Low	135	34.5
Medium/average	217	55.5
High	39	10
Total	391	100
Access to maternal care		
Low	188	48.1
Average	160	40.9
Highly	29	7.4
Very highly	14	3.6
Total	391	100

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025

Tables 2 above shows the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents. From the table, 25.8% respondents fall within 25-29 years range while 2% respondents fall between the ages of 45-49 years. The table also indicates that 31.5% respondents are males while 68.5% of the respondents are female. On the marital status of respondents, 45% respondents are married while 34.5% respondents are divorced/widowed. Furthermore, the table shows the distribution of respondents according to occupation with 26% respondents into farming and 39.4% respondents into business and commerce. On the level of education, 49.1% respondents have attended at least primary school, 27.9% respondents have secondary education, and 14.1% respondents have tertiary education while 8.9% respondents have no formal education. Also, 34.5% respondents affirmed to having low level of income while 55.5% respondents have medium/average level of income and 10% respondents have a high level of income. Lastly, the table shows that 48.1% respondents have low access to maternal care, 40.9% respondents have average access to maternal care while 7.4% respondents have high access and 3.6% respondents very highly access maternal healthcare.

Table 3: Correlation matrix of socioeconomic status and maternal care service

Socioeconomic status	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Level of income	1							
Cost of medical supplies	.057	1						
Women's level of education	.254*	.031	1					
Affordability of delivering in healthcare	-.232*	.009	-.046	1				
Women's lack of employment	-.080	-.337**	-.278**	.022	1			
Men's lack of employment	.105	-.321**	-.320**	.062	.204*	1		
Inability to save and raise money	.114	-.286**	-.327**	.012	.434**	.385**	1	
Access to maternal services	.288*	.207*	-.132	.218*	.198*	.227*	.127	1

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows the matrix of the relationship between socioeconomic status and access to maternal services. We can see that affordability of delivery service, level of income, women's lack of employment, cost of medical supplies and men's lack of employment are all significantly related to access to maternal health service. We can therefore reject the null hypothesis and state that there is a significant relationship between socioeconomic status and access to maternal health service in Lafia L.G.A., Nasarawa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings revealed that there is a relationship between socio-economic status of people and access to maternal healthcare services in Lafia L.G.A. The study discovered that level of income is a barrier affecting access maternal healthcare service because majority of the respondents concur to it. Here, the level of income of people matters because it is only when people have financial stability that they can be able to access maternal healthcare services, afford transportation fare to health facilities and also afford the bills for medication. This finding is supported by the work of Kaba, Taye, Gizaw and Mitiku (2017) that discovered that cost of transportation and financial dependence poses as hindrance to accessing maternal healthcare services. Due to the long distance, transport fares to health facilities, especially from rural areas are usually very expensive and way beyond the reach of rural dwellers, most of which are farmers.

The study also discovered that the affordability of delivering in healthcare facility acts as a barrier to access to maternal healthcare services in Lafia L.G.A. This is because of the standard of living of people in most rural areas in Lafia. This is also accompanied by women and men's lack of employment, both of which act as barriers affecting access maternal healthcare service.

This shows that the socio-economic status of people is one of the critical determinants of healthcare access as subscribing to health services may be capital intensive and the best way to tackle it will be financial buoyancy. The implication is that such burden lies more on rural dwellers than their urban counterparts; on this note, Hjorstborg and Mwikisa (2017) found that people residing in the rural areas pay a large proportion of their income than their urban counterparts when it pertains to healthcare because most sophisticated health facilities are located in urban areas and the urban dwellers pay less when it comes to transportation than rural dwellers. Studies by Bennett and Gilson (2019) and Hjorstborg and Mwikisa (2017) found that maternal mortality rate is high in low-income people and they are plagued with high rate of illnesses but use healthcare services more because of high cost of medical services.

Onah, Ikeako and Lloabachie, (2016), stressed the importance of socio-economic status to accessing healthcare facilities when they noted that fee-for-service is an impediment to women's use of maternal health services and keep millions of women from having hospital deliveries and seeking health care even when complications arise, most notably seeking the services of traditional birth attendants who are usually cheaper to patronize. This also hinders women from accessing adequate maternal care services during pregnancies and deliveries. According to a study by Yao, Murray and Agadjanian (2017), at the facilities, women often incurred additional expenses beyond the cost of services, such as the purchase of food while in care, however, women were frequently unable to comply due to lack of funds.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study assessed the socio-economic status of family and access to maternal health services in the area under study. The study reviewed literature pertinent to the research work and multistage sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study and the data gotten was processed and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science.

Furthermore, the study discovered that there is a nexus between level of income, level of education, employment and access to maternal healthcare services in Lafia L.G.A. as there is interplay between them. The paper therefor, recommended that, Health insurance scheme should be expanded to include farmers and women with little earning to contribute in order to make access and/or availability of such services to the poor.

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